

The zone of inhibition was found considerable for the species, *i.e.* *S. aureus* in the case of 2-(2-acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-phenylurea-*S*-triazine and 2-(2-acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-*o*-tolylurea-*S*-triazine (2.5 and 2.0 m.m., respectively). While the marked zone of inhibition was obtained for *E. coli* against 2-(2-acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-*m*-tolylurea-*S*-triazine and 2-(2-acetamidophenoxy)-4-anilino-6-*p*-nitrophenylurea-*S*-triazine (3 and 2 m.m., respectively.)

Infrared spectra : All the compounds in general recorded the following bands, N-H bending, 1540-1510 ; C-O stretching 1660-1600 ; C-O-C stretching 1240-1200 ; and C₈N₈ stretching 850-780 cm⁻¹.

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A Flavone Glycoside from Seeds of *Cassia spectabilis* DC

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IN an earlier communication¹ isolation of two anthraquinones and a flavone glycoside from the seeds of *Cassia spectabilis* DC along with the structural studies of the two anthraquinone derivatives had been reported. The present communication deals with the structural studies of the flavone glycoside.

The brown coloured flavone glycoside, C₂₃H₂₄O₁₁ when hydrolysed with ethanolic hydrochloric acid, gave glucose (PC, osazone) and an aglycone, C₁₇H₁₄O₆. On the basis of standard colour reactions², spectral data^{3,4} and chemical degradation studies, the aglycone has been identified as 5,4'-dihydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavone (velutin).

The aglycone showed bathochromic shift with aluminium chloride but the glycoside did not, indicating thereby that the glucose molecule is attached to the hydroxyl group at position 5. On periodate oxidation two moles of periodate per mole of the glycoside were consumed producing one mole of formic acid which showed that the sugar glucose is in the pyranose form. The hydrolysability of the glycoside by emulsin showed the presence of β-linkage.

The aglycone, velutin had been reported earlier from plant sources⁵ and it had been also synthesised⁶. Recently, a glycoside of velutin⁷, 4'-hydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavone-5-*O*-α-L(-) rhamnopyranoside has been reported from the seeds of *Cassia nodose*. But the glycoside in the present communication, 4'-hydroxy-7,3'-dimethoxyflavone-5-*O*-β-D(+)-glucopyranoside, isolated from the seeds of *Cassia spectabilis* is reported for the first time.

Experimental

Isolation and purification of the glycoside has been described in an earlier communication¹.

Hydrolysis : The glycoside (200 mg) was hydrolysed using 7% ethanolic hydrochloric acid (25 ml) under reflux for 6 h, ethanol distilled off and the aglycone crystallised from ethyl acetate, m.p. 225° (Found : C, 64.70 ; H, 4.70. C₁₇H₁₄O₆ calcd. C, 65.00 ; H, 4.50%) ; acetate (Ac₂O/Py), m.p. 207° (Found : acetyl 20. C₁₇H₁₂O₆(COCH₃)₂ calcd. 21.60%) ; methyl ether (Me₂SO₄/K₂CO₃), m.p. 192° (Found : methoxy 32.92. C₁₅H₈O₂(OCH₃)₄ calcd. 36.26%) ; λ_{max} (EtOH) 268, 348 ; +AlCl₃ 268, 383 ; +NaOEt 293, 398 nm ; ν_{max} (KBr) 3440, 2950, 2850, 1180, 1660, 1605 and 845 cm⁻¹ ; δ (DMSO) 3.85 (3H, s, OCH₃), 3.92 (3H, s, OCH₃), 6.35 (1H, d, *J* 2.5, C-6), 6.75 (1H, d, *J* 2.5 Hz, C-8), 6.90 (1H, s, C-3), 7.01 (1H, d, *J* 8.5 Hz, C-5), 7.60 (dd, *J* 2.5 Hz and 8.5 Hz, C-2', C-6').

Periodate oxidation : The glycoside (20 mg) was dissolved in ethanol (25 ml) and distilled water (25 ml), treated with 0.1 *M* sodium metaperiodate (25 ml) and the reaction mixture allowed to stand for 48 h. The amount of periodate consumed and formic acid liberated were estimated by titrimetric method of Hirst and Jones⁸. For each mole of the glycoside, 1.8 mole of periodate was consumed and 1.2 mole of formic acid liberated.

Enzymic hydrolysis : The glycoside (20 mg) was hydrolysed using emulsin prepared from almond⁹ at 40 to 50° for 12 h when D(+)-glucose was found in the hydrolysate(PC).

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Biflavones from Leaves of *Cupressus gracilis* and *Cupressus macrocarpa*

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THE genus *Cupressus* Linn¹. (Cupressaceae) consists of about twenty species. Cupressuflavone and amentoflavone seem to be characteristic biflavones to cupressaceae, hence they may serve as a useful taxonomic marker. The present paper deals with the isolation and characterisation of amentoflavone (1), sequoiافلavone (1a) and cupressuflavone (2) from these two species.

1, R=H
1a, R=OH,

2

The dried and crushed leaves of *Cupressus gracilis* (collected from Ooty) were extracted with

boiling acetone. The combined acetone extracts were concentrated under reduced pressure. The dark green gummy mass so obtained was refluxed with petroleum ether (b.p. 60-80°), benzene, ethyl acetate and acetone till the solvent in each case was almost colourless. The ethyl acetate and acetone fractions were mixed together and dried under reduced pressure. It was then purified on silica gel column, eluting successively with petroleum ether, benzene, benzene-ethyl acetate (1:1, 1:2), ethyl acetate and acetone. The last three fractions gave usual flavanoid colour test, they were combined and solvent distilled off to give yellowish brown solid. Tlc examination of crude mixture in benzene-pyridine-formic acid (36:9:5) revealed two spots, labelled as CI and CII in order of increasing Rf values. Both the bands were separated by plc (BPF) and eluted by acetone mixed with pyridine (2%).

CI obtained was methylated using dimethyl sulphate and potassium carbonate in dry acetone. The methylated mixture showed the presence of two components (tlc), and were separated by plc. The homogenous components were labelled as CIA and CIB.

CIA, m.p. 173-74°, Rf 0.40, confirmed as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7-hexa-O-methylamentoflavone². The structure of CIB was established as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, I-7, II-7-hexa-O-methylcupressuflavone by direct comparison of its methyl ether³ with that of authentic sample².

CII was characterised as I-4', II-4', I-5, II-5, II-7, pentahydroxy-I-7-O-methyl[I-3, II-8]biflavone (sequoiافلavone) by comparison of ¹Hnmr data of its acetate⁴ and methyl ether³ with those of authentic sample.

The dried and crushed leaves of *Cupressus macrocarpa* (procured from Ooty) were also investigated for biflavonyl pigments and led to the isolation and characterisation of the same biflavones, viz. amentoflavone, cupressuflavone and sequoiافلavone. The establishment of structures was made by comparison of physical data and pmr studies of their methyl ethers and acetates with those of authentic samples.

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